

STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT OF WIND POWER IN ASIA

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Abstract: The world's wind power can become a true driver of new job creation, employing more than 3.7 million people by 2030 and more than 6 million by 2050, according to a new IRENA report. These figures would be almost three and five times higher than the number of jobs, respectively, of just over a million in 2018. Sound industrial and labor policies that build on and in turn strengthen domestic value chains can boost incomes and employment by attracting existing economic activities to support the development of wind energy.

Keywords: renewable energy, Future of Wind, electrification, climate-friendly, offshore WPP, overground WPP.

In the modern world, the entire environment for humanity, more precisely, society has become dependent on electricity, even though it will be a building machine, tourism, pharmaceuticals, economics and other industries cannot develop without it. Because of this, the demand for electricity is increasing day by day in every sector of the world economy. As a result of a large amount of energy demand, minerals for fuel in electricity generation are quickly lost and this situation is a very big problem. This global problem can be called the rapid depletion of underground fossils. To solve this issue, alternative energy sources have been developed, more precisely, the generation of electricity from alternative energy sources that are obtained from nature.

Asia could increase its onshore wind power installed capacity from 230 GW in 2018 to over 2,600 GW by 2050, according to a new report from the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). By that time, the region will become a world leader in wind energy, accounting for more than 50 percent of all onshore installed capacity and more than 60 percent of all offshore capacity.

According to a report titled "The Future of Wind Energy" (Future of Wind), presented on October 21 at the China Wind Power event in Beijing, by 2050, global wind power could grow tenfold and cross the threshold of 6,000 GW. By mid-century, wind power could meet a third of the world's electricity demand and, combined with further electrification, reduce the energy industry's carbon emissions by a quarter, which is necessary to meet the terms of the Paris Agreement. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to annually increase the wind power capacity on land and offshore by four and ten times, respectively, compared to those available today.

"With the help of renewable energy sources, a climate-friendly future can be ensured," said Francesco La Camera, CEO of IRENA. "Affordable renewable energy technologies such as wind power are now available, which is the most effective and fastest solution to the problem of reducing carbon emissions into the atmosphere. It follows from our roadmap for global energy transformation up to 2050 that it is technically and economically feasible to ensure a climate-friendly and sustainable energy future. Unleashing the global potential of wind energy will be of particular importance. In fact, by mid-century, wind power could be the largest single energy source along the way.

The world's wind power can become a true driver of new job creation, employing more than 3.7 million people by 2030 and more than 6 million by 2050, according to a new IRENA report. These figures would be almost three and five times higher than the number of jobs, respectively, of just over a million in 2018. Sound industrial and labor policies that build on and in turn strengthen domestic value chains can boost incomes and employment by attracting existing economic activities to support the development of wind energy.

However, to accelerate the growth of global wind energy in the coming decades, increasing investment will be key. On average, international investment in the land sector should increase annually

from US\$67 billion to US\$211 billion (in 2050). As for the maritime sector, the average global investment by 2050 should increase from 19 to 100 billion dollars.

Main statistic indicators:

- By 2050, the Asian region will account for more than 50% of all onshore wind power installations in the world; North America (23%) and Europe (10%) will take second and third places, respectively. As for offshore wind energy, over 60% of all wind turbines will be concentrated in Asia; in Europe - 22%, North America - 16%.
- Directly in the home region, China will take the lead: the total installed wind power capacity in the country (on land and offshore) by 2050 will be 2,525 GW; followed by India (443 GW), South Korea (78 GW) and the rest of Southeast Asia (16 GW).
- Globally, the full present cost of electricity (LCOE) for onshore wind power will continue to decline to 2-3 US cents/kWh by 2050 from 6 cents/kWh in 2018. The cost of electricity generated from offshore WPP, expects a significant decline: to 3-7 cents/kWh by 2050 compared to 13 cents/kWh in 2018
- The nominal capacity of onshore wind turbines will increase from an average of 2.6 megawatts (MW) in 2018 to 4-5 MW (wind turbines commissioned by 2025). Sea-based installations, quite likely, can grow in terms of power up to 15-20 MW in one or two decades. By 2050, the capacity of floating wind farms may be about 5-15% of the total installed capacity of offshore wind farms worldwide (almost 1,000 GW).

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